

MARKETING STRATEGIES TO ANTICIPATE FOR SUSTAINABLE BUSINESSES SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES BEFORE AND DURING COVID-19

EDY YULIANTO

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Administrative Sciences University Brawijaya Malang.

ABSTRACT

Market research is such a specialised part of marketing that it is usually done by specialists, within either a marketer's organisation or an agency. The quality of the marketing decisions depends upon the quality of the marketing research on which they are based and its interpretation. It is, therefore, essential that marketers appreciate market research and what it can do. Markets are also busy so that competitors are also trying to find ways of capturing more customers or retaining their own. Marketing strategy, therefore, has three interdependent parts: segmenting markets into groups that can be served, ways of developing advantageous relations with those customers, and strategies to handle competitors. The study features an online survey and current scale sampling in the 250 respondents with data analyzed using structural equation modelling (SEM). Strategic marketing, the process of aligning the strengths of an organisation with groups of customers it can serve, it affects the whole direction and future of an organisation, so knowledge of the macro- and microenvironments and the markets served needs to inform the process. The paying attention to the spectacular aspect of the marketing strategy for SMEs, it is "Tangibles, Empathy, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance (TERRA)".

Keyword: Marketing Strategies, Sustainable Businesses, Terra, Before and During Covid-19.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since its emergence in late 2019, the COVID-19 epidemic has caused negative effects on the economies of countries. The conditions and restrictions imposed in most countries to limit the virus's spread among people, such as social distancing and quarantines, have led to distortions in the system of supply and demand for goods and slowed many countries' economies. The repercussions of the COVID-19 pandemic have been felt across all economic sectors and institutions, including small and medium enterprises SMEs (Hasanat et al., 2020).

Sustainability is a crucial but difficult goal; managers of small, medium and large companies asked this question: "is genuine progress still possible and is development sustainable in the business competition during Covid-19 of course", this question must be proven by factual scientific studies with dimensions that exist in a rational and scientific context. So when Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) businesses close en masse, "an entire sector of the economy suffers, there is lower cash flow, higher debt and more unemployment". That leads to a big drag on the eventual recovery. Because, "they are such an important source of jobs, losing them the way we are losing them now is going to make things far worse than they otherwise need to be. SMEs businesses account for more than 44 percent of all country economic activity, condisi Covid-19 and closures on such an immense scale could devastate

the country's economic growth". If they were grouped together, small businesses would be among the country's biggest employers.

Many studies continuously report that the government closure and stopping of these public places have not only reduced the number of cases of the Covid-19 but also has affected various obstacles for many economic, educational, and religious activities which are now entering the sixth month of experiencing the difficulties arise in various community business as well as the government activities (Bocken et al., 2014; Subroto, 2020). The impact of Covid-19 on the community's lives that needs joint attention because of this impact is becoming a matter of human health and the economic losses in various national and regional sectors. Therefore, this typical trend requires collective support and thought so that these conditions are solved immediately. Referring to much literature, the production sector and human welfare have become the most detrimental targets, so this requires practical solutions to revive the economy, especially through various strategies of people's business activities which have now reached the lowest growth rates since the last ten years (Joyce & Paquin, 2016; Crick, 2020; Hofacker, 2020).

One important aspect in business is how to manage customer loyalty. Covid-19 pandemic has forced business sale to decline. Therefore, giving optimum service and maintaining long-term relationship with customers are the keys to maintain sale transaction. Strengthening customer relationship may help SMEs to maintain their performance (Indah & Devie, 2013; Mozaheb et al., 2015; Hoque et al., 2017). Customer relationship-oriented sale requires the sellers to collect information about customers, to conduct segmentation, to create value with differentiation, and to create value toward profitability (Reijonen & Laukkanen, 2010). Other important factor that must be taken into consideration during Covid-19 pandemic is the efficiency of resource utilization. Resource efficiency is closely related with working capital management. Working capital has three roles, respectively being the power of life for the business, being one function of business sustainability, and being one aspect in financial management (Sadiq, 2017). The company that manages their working capital very efficiently would bear smaller risk on liquidity problem (Prasad et al., 2019). Working capital management that aims toward efficiency is a key for successful performance (Jamil et al., 2015; Utomo et al., 2018; Mabandla and Makoni, 2019).

It is likely that the COVID-19 crisis will have substantial consequences for our way of living, working and shopping, and more specifically for consumer behaviour. This means it will affect almost all businesses. To be able to continue meeting consumer's basic needs, and to maintain employment levels, companies must limit the damage as much as possible. One of the tools available to achieve this is marketing, Spectacular Marketing Strategies to Anticipate for Sustainable Businesses SMEs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Sustainable Marketing Businesses

Sustainability marketing is a way to build relationships with consumers while letting them know that they are important and so are future generations. While it is a developing field,

sustainability marketing is an important piece of marketing strategy. How many companies are there that can change? Sustainability marketing may just be the reason you choose a certain company over the many others out there (Loy, 2021). According to the thoughts of marketing experts quoted; a). Consumer oriented marketing; is when a company markets its products and services from a consumer's point of view. You want a message that shows the company is a better choice. This is marketing that consumers can see from their own perspectives (Agyapong & Boamah, 2013). Customer-value marketing; is when a company invests in building value with its customers. This means a company researches what their customers appreciate and markets those exact qualities to them. For example, with our company, we may focus our marketing on supporting our customer's lifestyles (Gurría, 2020; Segal & Gerstel, 2020).

Innovative marketing; the principle of innovative marketing ensures that an organization never stops finding better ways to develop products, services and better ways to market. Those that ignore innovation will lose customers to those that find better and better ways (Agyapong & Boamah, 2013). Sense of mission marketing; sense-of-mission marketing is the principle that guides a firm to define a broad mission that speaks to society rather than just the product. Adopting a broad mission gives a company a clear, long-term direction and serves the best long-run interests of consumers and the brand (Bartik et al., 2020). Societal marketing; with the principle of societal marketing, the company balances decisions based on the customer wants, the company requirements, and the customer and society's long-term interests. For example, Method home products put the hurt on dirt without doing harm to people, creatures or the planet. Innovative companies look ahead to potential societal issues as opportunities (Eggers, 2020).

Sustainability marketing can contribute to the Triple Bottom Line (TBL), which accounts for the environmental quality, social equity and economic prosperity in a way that can help marketers manage resources, capabilities and develop a competitive advantage (Chabowski, Mena & Gonzalez Padron, 2011). The environmental dimension is about responsibility with natural resources, the social dimension is about responsibility to society and the economic dimension is about value creation and firm financial performance. The economic dimension is important because companies that want to enact a social or environmental change must operate profitably or they will not survive to pursue their other goals (Tracey & Phillips, 2007). Using the healthy framework allows a more holistic understanding of consumer support for sustainable business that is theoretically grounded in Lundes (2018) conceptualization of sustainable marketing.

Talking about a sustainable business strategy means talking about a combination of business goals and the social environment that has integrated into the business goals, operations, management, and business planning that has determined towards long-term business sustainability that has highly valued for the business, employees, customers and surrounding communities (Evans et al., 2017; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018; Pieroni et al., 2019; Fernando et al., 2019). To develop fully sustainable strategies, they will need to develop new technologies. For example, detergent manufacturers have developed laundry products for

low-temperature washing. Some have embarked on a wash right campaign which promotes the virtues of low temperature washing by emphasising the benefits to the clothes as well as energy savings. Finally, companies can develop a sustainability vision, which serves as a guide to the future. It shows how the company's products and services, processes and policies must evolve and what new technologies must be developed to get there. This vision of sustainability provides a framework for pollution control, product stewardship and environmental technology (Kotler, 2011). Figure 1 depicts these five antecedent dimensions of consumers support for sustainable business, which serve as potential targets for sustainable marketing programs.

2. Tangibles Dimension

Zeithaml and Bitner (2003), identify tangibles as physical facilities (equipment, personnel, and communications materials). It is the physical image of the service that customers will use to assess quality. Tangibles are associated with the physical facilities, tools, and machines used in order to provide the service, as well as representations of the services, such as statements, cards (debit and credit), speed, and efficiency of transactions. Several privileges are included in tangibles such as; external appearance, counters in the business sector, overdraft facilities, opening hours, and speed and efficiency of transactions. stated that tangibles have the same importance as empathy (Saleem & Yaseen, 2017). The authors argued that it is advisable to consider including opening hours of operations under the empathy dimension; furthermore, the reliability dimension may include overdraft privileges, consider tangibles as a distinct element, showing consistency across cultures (Pai & Lin, 2018).

The fifth dimension of service quality is the Tangibility which is defined as the appearance of physical facilities, equipments, communication materials and technology. All these provide enough hints to customers about the quality of service of the firm (Caldera & Dawes, 2019). Also, this dimension enhances the image of the firm. Hence tangibility dimension is very important to firms and they need to invest heavily in arranging physical facilities (Leung, 2020).

H1: it is suspected that tangibles attitude toward business will positively influence support for sustainable business.

3. Empathy Dimension

Customers need to feel that they are made priority by the organization providing services. Empathy means caring, paying personal attention, and providing services to customers (Saleem & Yaseen, 2017). The core of empathy is conveying the feeling that the customer is unique and special. Stated that quantitative studies that have identified service quality model dimensions have used security, credibility, and access to measure empathy (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2003). Another dimension of service quality is the Empathy dimension. It is defined

as the caring, individualized attention provides to the customers by their or service firms (Pai & Lin, 2018). This dimension try to convey the meaning through personalized or individualized services that customers are unique and special to the firm. The focus of this

H2: it is suspected that Empathy will positively influence support for sustainable business.

dimension is on variety of services that satisfies different needs of customers, individualized or personalized services etc. In this case the service providers need to know customers personal needs or wants and preferences (Leung, 2020).

4. Reliability Dimension

That reliability means organizations perform a service correctly the first time. Moreover, it shows that organizations strive to fulfil promises and pay attention to the results. Reliability has been classed as the first dimension of the servqual service quality model (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2003). Studies of Lam ranked reliability as first in the dimensions of the service quality model (Pai & Lin, 2018). Reliability is defined as the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. In broad sense reliability means, service firm's promises about delivery, service provisions, problem resolutions and pricing (Caldera & Dawes, 2019).

Customers like to do business with those firms, who keep their promises. So it is an important element in the service quality perception by the customer and his loyalty. Hence the service firms need to be aware of customer expectation of reliability. In the case of business sector services, the reliability dimension includes - regularity, attitude towards complaints (Saleem & Yaseen, 2017).

H3 : it is suspected that valuing reliability will positively influence support for sustainable

5. Responsiveness Dimension

The responsiveness of willing employees involves telling customers exactly when things will be done, giving them undivided attention, promoting services, and responding in accordance with their requests. Responsiveness was ranked as the third dimension in servqual (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2003). Responsiveness is the willingness to help customers and to provide prompt service.

H4: it is suspected that responsiveness the practices of businesses will positively influence support for sustainable business.

This dimension focuses in the attitude and promptness in dealing with customer requests, questions, complaints and problems. It also focuses on punctuality, presence, and professional commitment etc., of the employees or staff (Saleem & Yaseen, 2017). It can be calculated on the length of time customers wait for assistance, answers to questions etc. The conditions of responsiveness can be improved by continuously view the process of service delivery and employees attitude towards requests of customers (Pai & Lin, 2018).

6. Assurance Dimension

Assurance has been defined as employee’s courtesy and knowledge, and their capacity to transfer confidence and trust to customers. The opinions of researchers on the ranking of assurance among service quality dimensions are varied. Assurance is ranked first according to Gronroos, while the author of ranked it in fourth place (Caldera & Dawes, 2019). Assurance means keeping customers informed in their native language and listening to them, regardless of their educational level, age, and nationality. Parasuraman et al. (2008) states that assurance indicates the attitudes of the employees and their behaviour, and the staff’s ability to provide friendly, confidential, courteous, and competent services.

The third dimension of service quality is the Assurance dimension. It can be defined as employee’s knowledge, courtesy and the ability of the firm and its employees to inspire trust and confidence in their customers (Caldera & Dawes, 2019). This dimension is important in business sector, insurance services because customers feel uncertain about their ability to evaluate outcome. In some situations like insurance, stock broking services firms try to build trust and loyalty between key contact persons like insurance agents, brokers etc and individual customers (Pai & Lin, 2018). In business sector services "personal business sector" plays the role of key contact person. This dimension focuses on job knowledge and skill, accuracy, courtesy etc of employees and security ensured by the firm (Leung, 2020).

III. METHODS

The current study is limited to SMEs in Saudi Arabia that employ a number of employees, ranging between six and 250 the online questionnaire prepared through was used to collect the data. To test hypotheses 1-5, we collected data using an online survey that assessed the focal constructs of our conceptual model.

H5: it is suspected that responsiveness the practices of businesses will positively influence support for sustainable business.

Figure 1: In the Conceptual Model

The purpose here was to explain possible antecedents of consumer support for sustainable business. Our primary analysis consisted of structural equation modelling (SEM) using stats 15 to analyze the data and to evaluate the five hypotheses we proposed. We elected to utilize SEM due to its ability to account for measurement error and test the fit of the model to the data (Kline, 2015). We collaborated with SMEs Malang, to make certain that our 250 respondents were from the SMEs Malang. And that the study featured a representative panel. In important ways, the sample proved to be representative as follows: (51.50% female mean age 30 - 40 years and 48.50% male mean age 40 - 50 years). Most of these respondents have upper secondary education (45%) then some have quite high education (35%) and only a few have low education (20%).

Each participant completed an online survey that included measures of the following constructs: (1) tangibles for sustainable business is important; (2) then for empathy for sustainable business also need attention; (3) Reliability for sustainable business is an aspect that needs to be considered by the business; (4) Responsiveness for sustainable business juga menjadi bagian yang tidak boleh diabaikan pemilik usaha; (5) Lastly, assurance for sustainable business is the key in maintaining business continuity during the Covid-19 period and before.

This study operational zed constructs representing core elements of the five dimensions of the healthy framework of sustainable marketing (Lunde, 2018). Unless otherwise noted, we employed or adapted questions from previous research and used seven-point Likert-type scales. Table 1 presents the survey items of the study along with their descriptive statistics, the factor loadings for the items, as well as each corresponding constructs average variance extracted, and reliabilities. measurements for constructs and items, has a high alpha value of more than .50 and a mean value of more than 4.00, so that this dimension of service quality contributes to business sustainability for SMEs.

Table 1: Measurements for Constructs and Items

	α	Mean	SD	Final Loading
1. Tangibles for sustainable business	.76			
- The physical appearance of the facilities		4.13	1.02	.74
- The physical appearance of the staff		4.07	1.04	.76
- The physical appearance of the buildings		4.09	1.07	.78
3. Valuing Empathy for sustainable business	.80			
- Provide caring individualized attention		4.07	1.54	.85
- Company does best to satisfy his needs		4.11	1.39	.88
- To their maximum to meet the demands of customers		4.33	1.50	.79
3. Reliability for sustainable business	.84			
- The ability to same level of service again		4.33	1.33	.93
- Ability to same level of service down		4.06	1.65	.87
- Is ability to same level of service <u>excelex</u>		4.08	1.73	.90
- Feedback regarding progress always given		4.61	1.43	.87
- Are messages always passed on		4.03	1.38	.93
- Like to invest has paid its employees up to five service		4.39	1.80	.88
4. Responsiveness for sustainable business	.83			
- It is the willingness to help customers		4.06	1.40	.77
- It is the provide prompt service		4.09	1.55	.83
- Emphasizes attentiveness in dealing with customers		4.87	1.33	.90
- Emphasizes attentiveness in dealing with customers		4.01	1.60	.83
- Emphasizes attentiveness in complaints and problems		4.88	1.44	.91
5. Assurance for sustainable business	.89			
- It means to inspire trust and confidence		4.56	1.41	.84
- is really important for to build trust		4.57	1.39	.80
- is really important for to manage risks		4.63	1.34	.79
- is really important for to <u>maximise</u> opportunities		4.55	1.49	.81
- can build and demonstrate trustworthiness		4.36	1.35	.86
6. Support for sustainable business	.82			
- Increase business income		4.03	1.83	.83
- Fixed income only		4.14	1.46	.81
- is a decrease in the results of the effort		4.31	1.55	.79
- More, for data to flow and create business value		4.09	1.67	.87

This research developed a construct to measure spectacular marketing strategies to anticipate for sustainable businesses SMEs before and during Covid-19. The next step is to analyze the relationship or influence of each variable to measure the value for sustainable businesses at SMEs, which becomes a reference material for the implications of entrepreneurs and owner.

IV. RESEARCH AND RESULTS

Researchers in the study first tested each constructs one factor structure using principle components analysis with direct oblimin rotation. As expected, our analyses revealed one factor for each newly developed construct and Eigen values greater than one for the one-factor structure of both constructs, explaining 71.5% of the variance for attitude toward business benevolence and 66.5% of the variance for concern about business ethical practices.

We examined the full measurement model using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) with all model variables to ensure the items reflected their appropriate latent constructs. A six-factor model fit the data well ($\chi^2(295) = 469.45$, $p < .001$; CFI = 0.92; SRMR = 0.07; RMSEA = 0.06) and all factor loadings were substantial ($> .54$) and significant ($ps < .001$). The comparative fit index (CFI) provides a measure of model fit compared to other models, while the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) represents the standardized difference

between the observed and predicted correlation. Lastly, the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) is the standard deviation of the predicted errors (Kline, 2015).

Next, following the suggestions of Fornell and Larcker (2001), we tested for convergent and discriminant validity. Analyses supported convergent and discriminant validity of our constructs in the following ways: (1) AVEs extracted for all constructs exceeded the suggested value of .50 except for valuing social justice (i.e., .47); (2) the AVEs exceeded the squared correlation between constructs; and (3) the composite reliabilities for all constructs showed healthy convergence of the items ($> .73$). Because the measure for valuing social justice was drawn from Schwartz's (1992) established value survey, we opted to retain all three items for this construct.

We assessed common method variance in the following manner. First, we ran Harman's one-factor test (Korsgaard & Roberson, 1995; Mossholder, Bennett, Kemery, & Wesolowski, 1998). Loading all items from the latent variables on one-factor in a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) resulted in a CFA model that did not fit the data well ($\chi^2 (274) = 219.52, p < .001$; CFI = 0.50; RMSEA = 0.16). Second, we introduced a common-method-factor to our six-factor measurement model (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, & Podsakoff, 2003). The CFA with the common method factor showed that the additional factor accounted for less than 4% of the variance in the indicator variables. In sum, common method variance did not pose a problem in the study.

Table 2 presents the correlation matrix, descriptive statistics, AVEs, and composite reliabilities of the model constructs. The correlation table of table 2 shows consumer support for sustainable business was positively related to both valuing nature and social justice, attitude toward business benevolence, concern about business ethical practices, and business contributions to consumer's quality of life.

The initial structural model was estimated with ML (maximum likelihood), resulting in adequate fit indices ($\chi^2 (308) = 716.52, p < .001, RMSEA = .07, CFI = .95, SRMR = .12$). Although correlations specified in our initial model emerged with statistical significance, two of our five direct paths did not emerge with significance. The final structural model run without the non-significant paths resulted in adequate fit indices once again ($\chi^2 (293) = 674.53, p < .001, RMSEA = .07, CFI = .95$). Notably, the final model fit-indices remained unchanged from the initial model.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Tangibles for sustainable business	1.00					
2. Empathy for sustainable business	.55**	1.00				
3. Reliability for sustainable business	.41**	.57**	1.00	1.00		
4. Responsiveness for sustainable business	.27**	.40**	.45**	.44**	1.00	
5. Assurance for sustainable business	.21**	.25**	.31**	.35**	.40**	1.00
6. Support for sustainable business <u>SMEs</u>	.46**	.25**	.38**	.42**	.56**	.47**
M	5.45	5.81	5.75	5.22	4.95	4.88
SD	1.25	1.18	1.22	1.15	1.06	1.15
AVE	.61	.54	.50	.46	.41	.37
Composite Relianility	.83	.78	.72	.65	.58	.45

Notes : $p < .05$ or $p < .01$ (two-tailed) $n = 250$

As can be seen in Fig. 2, three exogenous constructs posted statistically significant standardized path coefficients at $p = .05$ when regressed on support for sustainable business (attitude toward business benevolence, valuing nature, and concern about business ethics).

Interpretation 1; Tangibles Dimension

Since services are tangible, customers derive their perception of service quality by comparing the tangible associated with these services provided. It is the appearance of the physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials. In this survey, on the questionnaire designed, the customers respond to the questions about the physical layout and the facilities that offer to its customers, the existing influence (46%) is for tangibles for sustainable business, so H1 is proven with a fairly strong value.

Interpretation 2; Empathy Dimension

It means to provide caring individualized attention the firm provide its customers. In some countries, it is essential to provide individual attention to show to the customer that the company does best to satisfy his needs. Empathy is an additional plus that the trust and confidence of the customers and at the same time increase the loyalty. In this competitive world, the customer's requirements are rising day after day and it is the companies' duties to their maximum to meet the demands of customers, else customers who do not receive individual attention will search elsewhere. There is sufficient influence (25%) of empathy for sustainable business, thus for H2 it is also proven with sufficient value.

Interpretation 3; Reliability Dimension

It is the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. Reliability means that the company delivers on its promises-promises about delivery, service provision, problem resolutions and pricing. Customers want to do business with companies that keep their promises, particularly their promises about the service outcomes and core service

attributes. All companies need to be aware of customer expectation of reliability. Firms that do not provide the core service that customers think they are buying fail their customers in the most direct way. Didapatkan nilai pengaruh yang cukup (38%) dari reliability for sustainable business, this means that for H3 it is proven to be at a sufficient level.

Interpretation 4; Responsiveness Dimension

It is the willingness to help customers and provide prompt service. This dimension emphasizes attentiveness and promptness in dealing with customer's requests, questions, complaints and problems. Responsiveness is communicated to customers by length of time they have to wait for assistance, answers to questions or attention to problems. Responsiveness also captures the notion of flexibility and ability to customize the service to customer needs. There is a fairly strong influence (42%) of responsiveness for sustainable business, so this result strengthens the evidence for H4 which is mentioned at a fairly strong level.

Interpretation 5; Assurance Dimension

It means to inspire trust and confidence. Assurance is defined as employee's knowledge of courtesy and the ability of the firm and its employees to inspire trust and confidence. This dimension is likely to be particularly important for the services that the customers perceives as involving high rising and/or about which they feel uncertain about the ability to evaluate. Trust and confidence may be embodied in the person who links the customer to the company, for example, the marketing department. Thus, employees are aware of the importance to create trust and confidence from the customers to gain competitive advantage and for customer's loyalty. Then there is a strong influence (56%) from assurance for sustainable business, in addition to the proven H5 hypothesis, the value of this variable is a big influence in SMEs before and during Covid-19.

Interpretation 6; Support for sustainable business SMEs

Learn to help SMEs adopt sustainability practices that benefit their communities, customers and financial positions, as well as the environment. Now that you know about sustainability and the triple bottom line, it's time to think about how they apply to your business. The marketing strategy for SMEs, it is "tangibles, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, assurance" (TERRA). These articles will provide you with a starting point so that you can use a framework to avoid ad hoc efforts, follow proven steps for sustainability, and overcome common challenges. Overall there is an influence (47%) of "tangibles, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, assurance" (TERRA) for sustainable businesses SMEs before and during Covid-19.

V. DISCUSSION

Whilst your marketing strategy might require regular adjustments or tweaks, it provides you with a template of where to start and makes it easier to see similar or improved results from each campaign without having to completely reinvent the wheel. It also creates stability and a sense of predictor within marketing department. Kotler (2011) mention; marketing strategy

to a menu; a menu is a repeatable process and a framework. For example, if your dinner menu during the Thanksgiving holiday is typically made up of turkey, stuffing, cranberry sauce, corn, and pumpkin pie, then it is probably fair to assume that this is going to be more or less the same each year.

Sustainability became important many decades ago, in one form or another, people have been advocating for sustainability for a long time. It is natural that their voices have not reached the business world, even with all the creative ideas, the typical structures based in a long-held beliefs face terrible objection (Martin and Schouten, 2012). Sustainability issues are modifying the relationship between business organizations and the business environment they exist in. The relationship between the business organization and the consumer is also changing and the sustainable marketer needs to learn how to address these situations in order to be successful. (Emery, 2012). For SMEs owners or their managers, in this competitive marketing, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, aspects of service quality must be a concern.

VI. CONCLUSION

The three predictors registering statistically significant influence on support for sustainable businesses; the most important thing is "assurance for sustainable business" then pay attention to the "tangibles for sustainable business" aspect, then add a touch on "responsiveness for sustainable business", but don't forget the dimension of "reliability for sustainable business" and the last thing to pay attention to is in terms of this is the dimension of "empathy for sustainable business" so that it can provide solutions for SMEs to survive and possibly thrive even in difficult conditions such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

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